

THE REFLECTION OF NATIONAL TRADITIONS IN THE CREATIVITY OF CONTEMPORARY UZBEK COMPOSERS

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Abstract: This article is intended for students studying musicology and composition, as well as students engaged in compositional creativity and creating works as composers based on national music. It also provides useful information for independent researchers and any researcher engaged in science.

Keywords: individuality, genre modification, genre syncretism, writing techniques of modern music, polyphony of rhythms.

The 20th century marked a period of significant social, spiritual, and moral transformation in human development. These changes were vividly reflected in the realm of art. The artistic directions, technical writing, and diverse genres and forms in the works created during this time draw our attention. Among these artistic developments, some common tendencies emerge. Notably, the spirit of the era and its unique styles are evident in the genres chosen by contemporary composers, allowing us to perceive the influence of the times through their works.

The synthesis of tradition and modernity in the works of composers has led to the creation of unprecedented examples. The essence of modern music is reflected in the following:

- A pursuit of individuality;
- A deep and analytical approach to folk music heritage, demonstrating the technical possibilities of 20th-century composition;
- The increasing significance of new trends in works based on various genres and forms.

The pursuit of individuality has introduced unique, unconventional compositions, replacing ancient forms. This quest for uniqueness, while rooted in tradition, has fostered the creation of works imbued with a modern spirit.

It is evident that the ongoing transformations in social life are increasingly expressed through new directions, styles, and genres. In showcasing the essence of the times, composers, particularly Uzbek composers, play a significant role.

One of the most notable phenomena in contemporary music is the drive to innovate musical writing techniques. These innovations are multifaceted, reflecting diverse tendencies. Like any novelty that builds on foundational elements, these changes in music are also implemented with a basis in ancient traditions. Innovations can manifest in various ways: new approaches to compositional styles, genre

reinterpretations (genre modifications), the integration of multiple genres in a single work (genre syncretism), and the combination of multiple styles within one piece (polystylism), among others.

National culture has been a key driving factor for innovations in contemporary music. One of the most important influences is the revival of traditional musical heritage. This includes not only the professional classical music legacy but also a deep interest in folk music, particularly folklore. This is evident in numerous works composed during the years of independence, where composers have succeeded in showcasing their unique writing styles. Consequently, each composer has introduced their individual style and novel techniques to the public through their works. For example, composers such as M. Tadjiev, T. Kurbanov, M. Bafayev, N. Giyasov, D. Saydaminova, A. Khoshimov, O. Abdullayeva, and D. Yanov-Yanovsky have significantly contributed to the development of modern interpretations of our national musical heritage.

From the second half of the 20th century, many works by Uzbek composers have been created based on programmatic music. These compositions often draw on national values, historical figures, religion, and heroic themes deeply rooted in the people's consciousness. Examples include M. Bafayev's "The Great Silk Road," "Alpomish," "Khoja Nasriddin," "Dhikr Al-Haqq," and "The Ancient Walls of Bukhara"; T. Kurbanov's "Toyana," "Abu Ali Ibn Sina," and "Pages of History"; and D. Saydaminova's "Memory of Friends."

Uzbek composers have been working in two primary directions within modern music:

1. Works created using contemporary techniques developed in European music.
2. Works that integrate these new techniques with the national musical heritage, particularly traditional music.

Alongside traditional expressive tools, new approaches and innovations in their application have paved the way for creative development. Modern music has seen a significant transformation in the roles of melody, rhythm, texture, harmony, and form. These changes have influenced thematic development, compositional principles, and the construction of musical texture and forms.

The concept of a theme, as described by many musicologists, encompasses a broad and multifaceted understanding. Historically, the notion of theme has evolved, reflecting the stylistic and directional shifts of each era. In the 16th century, the theme emerged as a concept associated with musical writing. By the end of the 18th century, it had become a structural aspect of musical form, acquiring a classical essence. In the second half of the 20th century, the theme began to be viewed in the context of dramaturgy within a composition.

In the 20th century, new perspectives on thematic concepts emerged in music theory, giving rise to novel approaches to musical themes in contemporary music.

These approaches were influenced by polyphonic thinking and new compositional techniques, including serialism, aleatoricism, sonorism, and pointillism.

Various types of themes exist, such as melodic, rhythmic, harmonic, timbral, and sonorous themes. By the 20th century, the concept of a complex theme had emerged. In addition, melodic themes in contemporary music began to be perceived on two levels: lyrical and figurative. Rhythmic themes often stemmed from folk music and played a significant role in Uzbek musical heritage.

Traditional rhythmic patterns (*usul*) are prevalent in both professional and folk Uzbek music, performed using percussion instruments like the *doyra* and *nogora*. These patterns serve multiple functions, appearing as themes, rhythmic frameworks, or textural components in compositions. Some works are entirely rhythm-based, a feature also applied in dance music.

Composers have integrated traditional rhythmic patterns into their creations, as seen in the symphonic works of T. Kurbanov and M. Tadjiev and the compositions of M. Bafayev. These rhythmic and melodic themes often alternate, influencing the overall structure of the piece. Similar to Uzbek classical music (*Shashmaqom*), stable rhythmic patterns serve as the foundation, while melodies evolve dynamically.

The influence of national traditions is evident in the semantics and structure of compositions. Variational principles, deeply rooted in traditional Uzbek music, are applied at both micro and macro levels. While traditional forms grow from a single melody, contemporary compositions often use thematic development through variation.

In conclusion, the processes of globalization have undoubtedly left their mark on musical culture. The trends of the 20th and 21st centuries have had a profound impact on the works of Uzbek composers. The pursuit of individuality has shaped compositional techniques, forms, and expressive tools, resulting in the emergence of new rhythmic, timbral-rhythmic, and textural-rhythmic thematic types. Traditional forms have evolved, and new forms have emerged due to internal and external factors, giving composers broader opportunities to explore genres, styles, and techniques. Notably, Uzbek musical heritage remains at the core of contemporary composers' work, harmonizing traditional interpretations with innovative possibilities from European music to achieve remarkable results.

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